

QSAR of substituted *N*-benzyl piperidines in the GBR series

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Abstract : Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) studies on substituted piperidine in the GBR series have been made. Significant correlations were obtained by multiparametric regression by using structural parameters with indicator parameters. The dopamine transporter (DAT) inhibitory activity of these compounds was found to increase with equalized electronegativity, hydrophobicity and bulk. The generated models were statistically validated using leave one out technique and cross validation methods.

Keywords : *N*-Benzyl piperidines in the GBR series, QSAR.

Introduction

The euphoric and reinforcing properties of cocaine are believed to be primarily associated with perturbation of the dopaminergic system¹⁻³, although other data strongly suggest that stimulant induced increase in norepinephrine contribute to the stimulant high^{4,5}. Cocaine is also a potent re-uptake inhibitor of serotonin (5-HT)⁶. The bioamine transporter such as dopamine transporter (DAT) acts as a useful pharmacotherapeutic agent for cocaine addiction and helps unravel the pharmacological mechanisms relevant to stimulant abuses. A series of 4-(2-bis(4-fluorophenyl)methoxy)ethyl-(substituted benzyl)piperidines with substituents at the *ortho* position in the aromatic ring of the *N*-benzyl side chain were synthesized by Boos and coworkers⁷.

The concept of Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) is to mutate searches for compounds with desired properties using chemical intuitions and experiences into quantified and computerized form. In this paper QSAR was performed on the series of twenty eight compounds having DAT inhibitory activity.

We report here the correlation of DAT inhibitory activity with physicochemical parameters with a view to provide a better rational approach for the design of the potent drugs in the GBR series. The physicochemical parameters such as Xeq (equalized electronegativity)⁸, log P (partition coefficient)⁹, $^1\chi^v$ (molecular connectivity)¹⁰, D (density)¹¹ and Id (information theoretic index)¹² have

been used in order to describe the role of different structural features of the drug molecules on the DAT inhibitory activity. The regression analysis was performed with the help of SPSS 7.5 version.

Results and discussion

N-Benzyl piperidine in the GBR series and their DAT inhibitory activity data as p(DAT) are listed in Table 1 along with the position of substituents. The entire data set of twenty eight compounds with the calculated values of physicochemical parameters and the indicator variables are given in Table 2. The autocorrelation among the physicochemical parameters for DAT inhibitory activity are shown in the correlation matrix in Table 3.

For the present QSAR studies, we have considered indicators variables I_1 to account for the presence of H at R_1 position, I_2 to account for the presence of CF_3 at R_1 position and I_3 to account for the presence of H at R_3 position and I_4 to account for the presence of F at R_4 position along with the structural parameters described earlier. A value of 1 was assigned for the presence and 0 for the absence of indicator parameters.

For the entire data set the best models were obtained with a combination of five parameters of which four are indicator parameters and the fifth a physicochemical parameter like electronic (Xeq), steric (D, Id, $^1\chi^v$) or hydrophobic (log P).

The following significant multi parametric QSAR models were obtained.

Table 1. Biological activities and position of substitution for substituted *N*-benzyl piperidine in the GBR series

Sr. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	Obs. p(DAT)
1.	H	H	H	F	F	8.432
2.	F	H	H	F	F	7.289
3.	Cl	H	H	F	F	7.174
4.	Br	H	H	F	F	6.979
5.	I	H	H	F	F	6.714
6.	CH ₃	H	H	F	F	7.319
7.	CF ₃	H	H	F	F	6.358
8.	CN	H	H	F	F	6.873
9.	NO ₂	H	H	F	F	6.870
10.	H	F	H	F	F	8.009
11.	H	Cl	H	F	F	8.585
12.	H	Br	H	F	F	8.658
13.	H	I	H	F	F	8.538
14.	H	CH ₃	H	F	F	8.357
15.	H	CF ₃	H	F	F	8.310
16.	H	CN	H	F	F	7.678
17.	H	NO ₂	H	F	F	7.959
18.	CF ₃	H	H	H	H	5.590
19.	CF ₃	H	H	F	F	6.893
20.	H	H	H	F	F	8.005
21.	H	H	F	F	F	8.745
22.	H	H	Cl	F	F	9.009
23.	H	H	Br	F	F	9.018
24.	H	H	I	F	F	8.721
25.	H	H	CH ₃	F	F	8.292
26.	H	H	CF ₃	F	F	8.854
27.	H	H	CN	F	F	8.921
28.	H	H	NO ₂	F	F	8.921

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters with indicator variables for substituted *N*-benzyl piperidine in the GBR series

Sr. No.	D	Xeq	log P	Id	¹ χ ^v	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃	I ₄
1.	1.135	2.260	6.680	13.306	11.782	1	0	1	1
2.	1.176	2.352	6.46	15.999	11.164	0	0	1	1
3.	1.196	2.345	7.030	15.999	11.297	0	0	1	1

Table-2 (contd.)

4.	1.298	2.343	7.180	15.999	11.945	0	0	1	1
5.	1.399	2.339	7.440	15.999	12.582	0	0	1	1
6.	1.129	2.326	6.960	15.999	11.475	0	0	1	1
7.	1.215	2.386	7.200	17.499	11.792	0	1	1	1
8.	1.200	2.347	5.750	15.999	11.449	0	0	1	1
9.	1.224	2.370	6.060	16.999	11.564	0	0	1	1
10.	1.176	2.353	6.460	15.999	11.158	1	0	0	1
11.	1.196	2.345	7.030	15.999	11.290	1	0	0	1
12.	1.298	2.343	7.180	15.999	11.933	1	0	0	1
13.	1.399	2.339	7.440	15.999	12.576	1	0	0	1
14.	1.129	2.326	6.960	15.999	11.469	1	0	0	1
15.	1.215	2.386	7.200	17.499	11.158	1	0	0	1
16.	1.200	2.347	5.750	15.999	11.443	1	0	0	1
17.	1.224	2.370	6.060	16.999	11.558	1	0	0	1
18.	1.215	2.386	7.200	17.499	11.792	0	1	1	0
19.	1.245	2.394	6.490	16.999	11.516	0	1	1	1
20.	1.410	2.332	6.310	15.499	11.058	1	0	1	1
21.	1.176	2.353	6.460	15.999	11.158	1	0	1	1
22.	1.196	2.345	7.030	15.999	11.210	1	0	1	1
23.	1.298	2.343	7.180	15.999	11.933	1	0	1	1
24.	1.399	2.339	7.440	15.999	12.576	1	0	1	1
25.	1.129	2.326	6.960	15.999	11.469	1	0	1	1
26.	1.215	2.386	7.200	17.499	11.158	1	0	1	1
27.	1.200	2.347	5.750	15.999	11.558	1	0	1	1
28.	1.224	2.370	6.060	16.999	11.792	1	0	1	1

Table 3. Correlation matrix among the physicochemical parameter parameters with indicator parameter

	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃	I ₄	Xeq	D	log P	Id	I _{χ^v}
I ₁	1.00								
I ₂	-0.457	1.00							
I ₃	-0.480	0.219	1.00						
I ₄	0.253	-0.554	-0.121	1.00					
Xeq	-0.244	0.525	-0.015	-0.262	1.00				
D	-0.026	-0.010	-0.053	0.032	0.128	1.00			
log P	0.039	0.113	-0.121	-0.155	-0.094	0.484	1.00		
Id	-0.207	0.454	-0.055	-0.291	0.949	0.110	0.015	1.00	
I _{χ^v}	-0.048	0.058	0.057	-0.076	-0.223	0.848	0.444	-	1.00

0.157

$$p(\text{DAT}) = 2.080 (\pm 4.778) \text{Xeq} + 1.746 (\pm 0.277) \text{I}_1 - 0.500 (\pm 0.491) \text{I}_2 + 0.443 (\pm 0.280) \text{I}_3 + 1.023 (\pm 0.671) \text{I}_4 + 0.683 \quad (1)$$

$$n = 26, R = 0.970, R^2 = 0.941, R_A^2 = 0.927, \text{S.E.} = 0.262, F_{(5,20)} = 64.069$$

$$p(\text{DAT}) = 0.326 (\pm 1.421) \text{D} + 1.742 (\pm 0.281) \text{I}_1 - 0.405 (\pm 0.445) \text{I}_2 + 0.428 (\pm 0.281) \text{I}_3 + 1.030 (\pm 0.681) \text{I}_4 + 5.170 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 26, R = 0.969, R^2 = 0.940, R_A^2 = 0.924, \text{S.E.} = 0.266, F_{(5,20)} = 62.124$$

Table 4. Calculated and residual values of different equations

Sr. No.	Eq. (1)		Eq. (2)		Eq. (3)	
	Calcd.	Resi.	Calcd.	Resi.	Calcd.	Resi.
1.	8.602	-0.184	8.741	-0.309	8.764	-0.332
2.	7.040	0.241	7.012	0.272	7.015	0.268
3.	7.028	0.145	7.019	0.155	7.051	0.123
4.	7.023	-0.045	7.052	-0.073	7.060	-0.081
5.	7.015	-0.302	7.085	-0.371	7.076	-0.362
6.	6.989	0.327	6.997	0.322	7.047	0.272
7.	6.613	-0.257	6.62	-0.263	6.647	-0.290
8.	7.033	-0.160	7.010	-0.147	6.978	-0.099
9.	7.080	-0.207	7.028	-0.158	6.991	-0.121
10.	8.345	-0.338	8.326	-0.317	8.317	-0.309
11.	8.331	0.253	8.333	0.256	8.353	0.233
12.	8.326	0.330	8.366	0.292	8.362	0.296
13.	8.318	0.218	8.398	0.139	8.378	0.160
14.	8.292	0.061	8.311	0.046	8.349	0.008
15.	8.416	-0.102	8.339	-0.029	8.363	-0.053
16.	8.336	-	8.334	-	8.273	-
17.	8.383	-0.422	8.416	0.383	8.293	0.339
18.	5.590	0.000	5.590	0.000	5.590	0.000
19.	6.637	0.257	6.630	0.263	6.603	0.290
20.	8.746	-	8.743	-	8.741	-
21.	8.790	-0.045	8.754	-0.009	8.750	-0.005
22.	8.792	0.234	8.761	0.248	8.785	0.224
23.	8.769	0.247	8.794	0.224	8.795	0.223
24.	8.761	-0.042	8.827	-0.106	8.811	-0.089
25.	8.735	-0.446	8.739	-0.446	8.781	-0.489
26.	8.859	-0.001	8.766	0.087	8.796	0.058
27.	8.779	0.141	8.766	0.159	8.706	0.215
28.	8.826	0.097	8.770	0.151	8.726	0.196

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{DAT}) = & 0.061 (\pm 0.216) \log P + 1.734 (\pm 0.279) I_1 \\
 & - 0.414 (\pm 0.446) I_2 + 0.433 (\pm 0.282) I_3 \\
 & + 1.057 (\pm 0.683) I_4 + 5.126 \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 n = 26, R = 0.969, R^2 = 0.940, R_A^2 = 0.925, \\
 \text{S.E.} = 0.265, F_{(5,20)} = 62.527
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{DAT}) = & 0.032 (\pm 0.149) I_d + 1.743 (\pm 0.281) I_1 \\
 & - 0.442 (\pm 0.475) I_2 + 0.436 (\pm 0.286) I_3 \\
 & + 1.043 (\pm 0.682) I_4 + 5.021 \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 n = 26, R = 0.969, R^2 = 0.939, R_A^2 = 0.924, \\
 \text{S.E.} = 0.266, F_{(5,20)} = 62.060
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{DAT}) = & -0.045 (\pm 0.349) {}^1\chi^v + 1.737 (\pm 0.280) I_1 \\
 & - 0.405 (\pm 0.436) I_2 + 0.425 (\pm 0.281) I_3 \\
 & + 1.029 (\pm 0.684) I_4 + 6.095 \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 n = 26, R = 0.969, R^2 = 0.939, R_A^2 = 0.924, \\
 \text{S.E.} = 0.267, F_{(5,20)} = 61.795
 \end{aligned}$$

where, n represents the number of data points, R is the correlation coefficient, R^2 is the coefficient of determination, R_A^2 is the adjusted R^2 and also known as explained variance which when multiplied by 100 gives the percentage of the variance in the activity that can be accounted for by the equation, S.E. is the standard error of estimate, F the variance ratio between the calculated and observed activities and data with (\pm) sign in parenthesis is confidence interval. In developing all the above models compound numbers 16 and 20 were treated as outliers.

In eq. (1), the sign of coefficient of equalized electronegativity (X_{eq}) is positive and sign of coefficient of indicator parameters I_1 , I_3 and I_4 are also positive and it

Fig. 1. A plot of comparison between observed versus calculated p(DAT) values using eq. (1).

clearly shows that on the one hand substituents with higher electronegativity will cause an increase in activity and on the other hand the presence of H at R_1 and R_3 positions and F at R_4 position will also have a positive effect on activity.

In eq. (2), the positive coefficient of D however shows that as the density of the group will increase the inhibitory activity of the compound.

In eq. (3), it may be noted that hydrophobic parameter $\log P$ was also playing important role in the interaction of the inhibitors with the enzyme. The positive sign of coefficient of $\log P$ reveals that more hydrophobic groups should be beneficial for activity. The sign of indicator parameters I_1 , I_3 and I_4 shows H at R_1 and R_3 position and F at R_4 position should be conducive for the activity.

In eq. (4), the information theoretic index (I_d) has positive sign of coefficient indicating that groups with more vertices should be preferred.

In eq. (5), ${}^1\chi^v$ is the first order Randic connectivity whose negative coefficient suggests that the branching is not favorable for the exhibition of DAT inhibitory activity.

It is interesting to record that in all the eqs. (1-5), it was observed that the coefficient of the indicator parameter I_2 which represents CF_3 at R_1 position is negative. This means that this group has a negative role in determining the activity and this group should be avoided at R_1 in the future drug designing.

In overall discussion all above given models are statistically significant and the values of all the statistical terms are significant. The high value of F test ($F_{(5,20)} = 4.56$) confirms the significance of the given equations. Standard errors of estimate of all the equations are very low. Calculated and observed values (difference between the observed biological activity and calculated activity)

for derived QSAR equations are reported in Table 4. The plot of observed versus calculated activity based on eq. (1) shown in graph (Fig. 1) and the predicted R_2 was fairly low.

As already stated in the discussion above, I_2 (CF_3 group) is not beneficial for drug modeling and hence it was not considered for further modeling. Multivariate correlation of DAT activity with physicochemical parameters gave so many equations but only best models are given here.

$$\begin{aligned} p(\text{DAT}) = & -0.038 (\pm 0.330) {}^1\chi^v \\ & + 0.125 (\pm 0.284) \log P \\ & + 1.800 (\pm 0.592) I_1 + 0.419 (\pm 0.334) I_3 \\ & + 1.403 (\pm 0.698) I_4 + 4.72 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} n = 26, R = 0.957, R^2 = 0.916, R_A^2 = 0.895, \\ \text{S.E.} = 0.312, F_{(5,20)} = 43.763 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} p(\text{DAT}) = & 0.121 (\pm 1.933) D \\ & + 0.101 (\pm 0.292) \log P \\ & + 1.802 (\pm 0.308) I_1 + 0.416 (\pm 0.334) I_3 \\ & + 1.395 (\pm 0.705) I_4 + 4.303 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} n = 26, R = 0.957, R^2 = 0.916, R_A^2 = 0.895, \\ \text{S.E.} = 0.3123, F_{(5,20)} = 43.662 \end{aligned}$$

In eqs. (6) and (7) the sign of coefficient of indicator parameters as well as the coefficients of $\log P$ and D are positive and coefficient of ${}^1\chi^v$ is once again negative. The values of the statistical terms are quite similar to those for eqs. (1) to (5).

In all the QSAR presented here the compound at the serial numbers 16 and 20 in Table 1 have been found not fit and this could be because any of the following reasons :

- (i) Outlier due to what seems to be congener but actually is not.
- (ii) Different rates of metabolism of the members of a set.
- (iii) The quality of experimental data.
- (iv) The parameter used may not be the best either obtained experimentally or evaluated otherwise.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) :

The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)¹³ is yet another parameter used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. We have calculated PE value of all the proposed models and are recorded them

Table 5. Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) and cross-validation parameters for the proposed models

Eq. No.	n	R	1-R ²	PE	6PE	Parameters used	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R _{cv} ²	PSE
1.	26	0.970	0.059	0.008	0.047	Xeq + I ₁ + I ₂ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.388	22.096	0.063	0.937	0.231
2.	26	0.969	0.060	0.008	0.047	D + I ₁ + I ₂ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.421	22.063	0.064	0.935	0.234
3.	26	0.969	0.060	0.008	0.047	log P + I ₁ + I ₂ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.412	22.072	0.064	0.950	0.233
4.	26	0.969	0.060	0.008	0.047	Id + I ₁ + I ₂ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.422	22.062	0.065	0.936	0.234
5.	26	0.969	0.060	0.008	0.047	¹ χ ^v + I ₁ + I ₂ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.428	22.052	0.065	0.935	0.234
6.	26	0.957	0.084	0.011	0.067	¹ χ ^v + log P + I ₁ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.649	21.834	0.076	0.925	0.252
7.	26	0.957	0.084	0.011	0.067	D + log P + I ₁ + I ₃ + I ₄	1.670	21.814	0.077	0.923	0.253

in Table 5. It is argued that of

- (i) $R < PE$, then correlation is not significant;
- (ii) $R > PE$; several times (at least three times), then correlation is indicated; and if
- (iii) $R > 6PE$, then the correlation is definitely good.

The data presented in Table 5 indicates that in all the cases R is much larger than $6PE$ indicating that all the proposed models have very good correlation.

Cross validation :

In addition the cross validation analysis was performed using leave one out (LOO) method^{14,15} in which one compound is removed from the data set and the activity is correlated using the rest of the data set. The cross validated R^2 was found to be very close to the value of R^2 for the entire data set. Final support in favor of our findings is obtained by using other cross validation methods¹³.

The essential feature of multiple regression analysis is cross validation which assesses the productivity of the computed model. Cross validation provides the value of PRESS, SSY and R_{cv}^2 from which we can investigate the predictive power of the proposed model. All the cross validation parameters are given in Table 5. It is argued that PRESS (predicted residual sum of squares) is a good estimate of the real predictive error of the model and if it is smaller than SSY (sum of squares of response value), the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant. Furthermore, the ratio PRESS/

SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compound. To be reasonable QSAR model, PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4 and the value of this ratio smaller than 0.1 indicates an excellent model. Also, if PRESS value is transformed in a dimension less term by relating it to the initial sum of squares, we obtain R_{cv}^2 i.e. the complement to the traces on of unexplained variance over the total variance. The high values of R_{cv}^2 confirm the significance of the models. However, for practical purposes of end users the use of square-root of PRESS/N, which is called predictive square error (PSE), is more directly related to the uncertainty of the predictions. The PSE values also support our results. The calculated cross validated parameters confirm the validity of the models developed and reported here.

At last a thorough study of all the statistically significant equations given above revealed that in future designing of this class of drugs with reference to their DAT inhibitory activity, the following points may be kept in mind :

- (i) More hydrophobic groups should be preferred.
- (ii) Smaller substituents having lesser branching and more electronegativity may be considered.
- (iii) H group at R₁ and R₃ and F at R₄ position may be retained.
- (iv) CF₃ at R₁ position should be avoided.

These findings are in conformity with the finding of

Boos and coworker⁷. Since they have also stated that presence of hydrogen at position R₁ and R₃ is beneficial towards the DAT inhibitory activity.

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